

Review of: Sarah Lamdan: Data Cartels. The companies that control and monopolize our information. Stanford University Press 2023¹

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Motivations for writing a book are many - here it is the story of a disappointment. Lamdan, a law professor who also worked as a law librarian for many years, spent a lot of time training on the Westlaw (Thomson Reuters) and Lexis (RELX) databases. Then in 2017, someone dropped an article on her desk that revealed how Thomson Reuters and RELX were vying to develop a data-driven surveillance system for U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement (ICE).

In the nascent Trump era, ICE had solidified its reputation, in Lamdan's account, as a brutal organization that tore apart families of people who had lived in the U.S. their entire lives, raided workplaces for deportations and locked children in cages. Lamdan began to have doubts. Both libraries and lawyers have high standards of trust and confidentiality - what was happening? Was she training immigration attorneys on tools that helped ICE detain their clients? Was library user data flowing to ICE? Lamdan did what she had always done when she had questions: she contacted customer service. If they had gone to extreme lengths so far to help the diligent multiplier of RELX products, they now abruptly lowered the blinds - and more than that:

„RELX, especially, exerted its power. A Lexis representative started camping out at my law school, calling my work phone, and my boss, demanding that I speak to her manager. She also started monitoring me through my students, asking them to report back to her if I talked about LexisNexis's ICE contracts. A blog post that a librarian and I wrote about the issue for the American Association of Law Librarians was erased moments after it was posted, and the organization replaced it with a single sentence: *„This post has been removed on the advice of General Counsel.“*“ (p. Xf.)

Sarah Lamdan was not intimidated and wrote this book. In it, she takes on Thomson Reuters and RELX as exemplars of a type of company she calls a *data cartel*. These cartels could span many business areas: RELX and Thomson Reuters are not only dominant in legal information, but are relevant players in science communication as a whole, furthermore in financial and business information, in the news business, and - currently more and more - in data brokering. Lamdan discusses these business areas one after the other and makes clear that the basic structure of these cartels is always the same: they transform important public goods into club goods in order to be able to control and market them in a privileged manner.

¹ This text is a machine-based translation of my review in order to provide easier access for non-German speaking interested parties, also the German language quotes were therefore transferred. Consider this version a »post-print derivative« and please refer to the original in case of references or citations: Siems, R. (2022). Rezension zu: Data cartels : the companies that control and monopolize our information / Sarah Lamdan. *O-Bib. Das Offene Bibliotheksjournal / Herausgeber VDB*, 9(4), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/5902>

Club goods privatize public goods by limiting access to them, thereby creating exclusivity. Those who have access do not necessarily have an interest in removing the access barrier, because the exclusivity of a beach resort depends precisely on the fact that just Dick and Harry cannot be there - even though there might be enough space. Club goods also exist in the digital realm, and they are particularly hotly contested there because there is usually no competing consumption in the digital realm. Otherwise, if the schnitzel that Dick eats is no longer available for Harry's plate, digital information can be copied without loss and consumed in parallel. Nevertheless, club goods also ensure exclusivity in the digital world by restricting access. One method for this is well known to us in libraries, it is the paywall. The e-book could have many more parallel readers, but the publisher's license limits access and thereby stimulates the price, which is currently an issue especially with textbooks,² and the state of affairs at the journals has already been classified as bizarre even by the investment bankers at Deutsche Bank.³

When we hear the term data cartels, we think of the big Internet corporations with their dubious practices that, with decades of delay, are now slowly becoming the subject of regulation as in the current European data legislation that explicitly targets GAFAM, the conglomerate of Google, Apple, Facebook, Amazon and Microsoft. The cartels Lamdan discusses are smaller and thus sail through below the thresholds set by the EU's Digital Markets Act, for example - and often enough below the attention threshold. Against this, Sarah Lamdan writes her book. Her core message is that the data cartels she discusses using RELX and Thomson Reuters as examples are the 'GAFAM of curated information.' Their goal is a 'Google without junk' (cf. p. 12) with condensed information for the decision-making level. Hence the fundamental tendency to club goods: the decision maker builds on information that is precisely not available to all. Consequently, the GAFAM of curated information should be viewed no less critically than, say, Meta Platforms Inc. but remains in the slipstream of regulatory attention.

"The truth is paywalled, but the lies are free"⁴ - data cartels thus create a powerful societal bias for Sarah Lamdan, a bias as the social sciences say, as they limit the ability of the broad mass of citizens to make informed decisions about their finances, their health or their rights. Instead, tracking gathers information about them so that they then become objects of others' decisions, rather than deciding for themselves. "Who decides, who decides?" was already the prominent question for Shoshana Zuboff in *Surveillance Capitalism*,⁵ and Lamdan follows her in analyzing that this is a particular form of exploitation because it is not just any products, but virtually intimate outpourings of our personalities that are being monetized here:

„The goods and services data analytics companies provide aren't merely products we buy and sell, they are products derived from us. Data analytics companies capitalize on the invisible, ethereal products of our minds. Industrials profited from mining, logging, and other trades that

² Campaign to investigate the ebook market for libraries. Online: <<https://academicebookinvestigation.org/>>

³ Cf. Klein, Samuel: Turning the Supertanker. Deutsche Bank on Elsevier's excess, Notes from the Knowledge Futures Group, Aug. 05, 2019, <https://notes.knowledgefutures.org/pub/supertanker/release/3>. Cf. the categorization in Gerhard Lauer, Datentracking in den Wissenschaften. Wissenschaftsorganisationen und die bizarre Asymmetrie im wissenschaftlichen Publikationssystem, in: o-bib 9 (1), 2022, pp. 1-13. Online: <https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/5796>.

⁴ Robinson, Nathan J.: The truth is paywalled but the lies are free. The political economy of bullshit, Current Affairs, 02.08.2020, <https://www.currentaffairs.org/2020/08/the-truth-is-paywalled-but-the-lies-are-free/>.

⁵ Zuboff, Shoshana: Das Zeitalter des Überwachungskapitalismus, Frankfurt am Main; New York 2018, S. 382.

strip value from our land, but unlike historical extractive ventures, data isn't cut from trees or extracted from earth, it's harvested from humans. Companies like RELX or Thomson Reuters appropriate our informational labour. They siphon intellectual and social output, co-opting our artistic and scholarly work and vacuuming up the digital exhaust we release through our wearable devices and online activities. They take things we make, turning our output into something they can own and store like wheat in silos." (p. 6)

This kind of transformation illustrates two things: what can be stored in the silo of product ownership does not have to take the form that meets actual needs, for one thing. There are many forms of digital scholarly communication that are much closer to the needs of research than the PDF of a paper medium - but that won't get you through an evaluation until the incipient reform of research assessment⁶ is further along. On the other hand, there is always a social relationship behind the technological illusion, as Meredith Whittaker currently illustrates for AI:⁷ someone selects the training data, they are supposed to say something about someone, someone else draws conclusions from it - it is a question of hierarchy and power, which is continuously growing and is also strengthened by the developments of earlier years, where, from Lamdan's point of view, competition law was increasingly restricted, even if this damaged competitors and democracy.

It is also this development that makes the current transformation towards APC-driven open access so questionable: this leaves traffic on the corresponding private company platforms, and thus information behavior can be further monitored. Together with content, it is to the cartels what the ever-growing mountain of past search queries is to Google - source material for predictive products, as Zuboff calls them, that make future action and thus trends saleable.⁸ For Lamdan, size is the decisive factor (and the driver for the countless acquisitions in the information sector) - RELX and Thomson Reuters have now reached a high level at which they can pull out ever new data products from the mass of data available to them like Matyoshka dolls, a double dipping with data assets.

The data products would not only grow out of economies of scale, they would also benefit the big players the most: corporations and government institutions that decide who gets insurance, who gets surveillance, who gets social benefits, who gets custody of the children. Data cartels reach far into government decision-making: Thomson Reuters and RELX both have hundreds of contracts with public agencies in the U.S. alone and have revolving doors of personnel. Thus, they are the "informational landlords that decide who can swim in the ocean of knowledge." (p. 16)

Lamdan sees the transition from the former publisher to the current data analytics company as a reduction in quality for users of the data cartels, since the technology can be overwhelmed by the mass of data for all investments. In addition, there is a lack of transparency: one only sees an infinite amount of data flowing in and data products coming out again (cf. p. 17). Overpolicing also occurs due to faulty dossiers, and not only among the known disadvantaged groups. But with the dynamic growth of the data cartels' risk assessment business lines, data-

⁶ Cf. the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), <https://coara.eu/>, and the Paris Call on Research Assessment, <https://osec2022.eu/paris-call/>.

⁷ Cf. Wolfangel, Eva: „KI ist eine Technik der Mächtigen“, in: MIT Technological Review 2022 (6), p. 22–25.

⁸ Cf. Zuboff 2018, p. 22.

based decision systems would nonetheless be introduced into more and more areas, such as youth services, leasing, banking, and insurance. The fuzzy talk of 'security', when what is actually meant is surveillance, does not in any way cause crime to fall, only discrimination and the number of people in prison to rise as a result. The public sector, which enabled the rise of the data cartels in the 1990s by simply giving away their databases (see pp. 28-30), is now the biggest customer - RELX alone sells data products to more than 7,500 institutions, such as the police, in the USA - and uses the opportunity to circumvent legal principles such as the inviolability of the home through 'data shopping'. You don't need a warrant to search a database, you just query it:

„Today, RELX runs its own private, third-party data center where thousands of law enforcement agencies consolidate and share their data. The company's Public Safety Data Exchange compiles federal, state, and local law enforcement data, links it to our LexIDs, and is available to RELX customers in products with names like ‚Accurint Virtual Crime Center.‘“ (p. 37)

Because of the social bias, the data cartels thus usually react quite indifferently to errors in their systems: in case of doubt, it is the others, the 99%, who are affected and disadvantaged - in this respect, errors are only technical, never a question of empathy or appropriateness. If Anatole France still wrote of the "law that forbids the rich as well as the poor to sleep under bridges, to beg in the streets and to steal bread",⁹ now not even this mockery has any basis anymore.

In the chapter on 'Academic Research,' which is closest to us with the field of information, Lamdan sums up many all-too-familiar things: the power position of the publishers, which has just been greatly enhanced by the metrification of academia; the pacing role that Elsevier has often had for the industry in the past; and the legal constraints from digitization when libraries no longer own, but only license. She reminds us that access to scientific information is a human right according to the UN Charter and that Open Science must be thought of together with Open Society - which is completely negated by the publishers' practiced club goods model and their turn to the data analytics business: "Instead of focusing on selling critical scientific information at an affordable price, the company is concentrating on developing software that sifts through the company's 'vast corpus' of academic data to draw 'insights' from - and monetize - the entire research process." (p. 51)

Such an approach requires investment, of course, and Lamdan calculates where the money needed to do so comes from: "If it only costs Elsevier \$600 to publish an article and Elsevier makes \$4,000 from selling it, what happens with the other \$3,400?" (p. 62) Even subtracting a 30% return on investment, there is a lot of money left, which is used by Elsevier and the other big players to buy out the market of innovations in the field of scholarly communication and to build entire data ecosystems.¹⁰ Libraries thus not only overpay, but subsidize what Zuboff calls the 'extraction imperative': from the volume of data, new products are created, which in turn generate even more data, which in turn are extracted and monetized - while the overall system becomes continuously more immersive in an effort to model the incentive systems and thus

⁹ France, Anatole: Die rote Lilie. Roman. Aus dem Französischen übersetzt von Caroline Vollmann, Zürich 2003, S. 147.

¹⁰ See the visualizations in Universiteit Utrecht: Innovations in scholarly communication. Changing research workflows, <https://101innovations.wordpress.com/>.

the course of research according to its own premises, not those of scholarship. According to Lamdan, hardly anyone at universities is aware of this concatenation of individual applications into entire workbenches, since no one has an overview of all the workflows (cf. p. 66).

With the turn to AI systems, publishers again significantly increase existing inequalities in science, because "machine-generated journal impact metrics and researcher ranking systems incorporate the same biases, white supremacy, and systemic racism that permeate academia, favoring the work of white men at elite institutions. Academic data analytics don't repair the racist and misogynistic decisions made in university tenure committees and college boards, they datafy them." (p. 63f.)

This bias produced by the introduction of AI systems also makes itself felt in legal information for Lamdan in the following chapter. Through assistance systems and algorithms, the platforms are designed to suggest readings of the law, promising cases and counter-arguments to users which they know very well - an independent search and formation of judgment by the users thus takes place less and less. Through this guidance, the databases marketed by RELX and Thomson Reuters gain a law-forming power, and this against the background that the ordering basic systematics of the systems originate from the time of the American Civil War. "It's not surprising that products based on John B. West's 1800s-era legal classification system 'reflect a nineteenth century worldview' that institutionalizes the white, male, heteronormative, upper-class, able-bodied and political conservative perspective." (p. 76)

Legal information, she argues, is as much a critical infrastructure as academia, and its copyright-protected monopolization into club property is devastating for all dependents: about 70% of a law firm's budget went to RELX and / or Thomson Reuters. For people who cannot afford a lawyer, even the simplest exercise of their rights becomes almost impossible, because the state let the era of paper documents expire and migrated to digital formats - but did not create an adequate infrastructure for their use. As a result, those who serve time in deportation centers because ICE tracked them down based on data provided by RELX and Thomson Reuters are completely dependent on the same companies' digital *Prison Products*, with severely limited functionality and in a language that many of those affected do not understand. It goes without saying that these kiosk computers, for their part, are crammed with tools for monitoring all the online activities of those who use them (cf. p. 85f).

For Lamdan, financial data is different from technical or legal information: it is not publisher-grade information, but neither is it unstructured information. This intermediate area is sometimes difficult to deal with; in Germany, the BERD consortium is doing so within the framework of the National Research Data Infrastructure.¹¹ The products of the data cartels would be described by them in a very blurred way, but premium priced. According to Lamdan, erroneous data 'correct themselves' because everyone uses them as if they were correct. In digitalization, there is an increasingly extreme asymmetry between data users and the general public with regard to the possibility of gaining economic advantages.

In the past, financial data already had a similarity to legal information, because access to it was protected by law for a long time, for example to contain the danger of a bank panic due to spread rumors - everyone should be able to inform themselves. The softening of this

¹¹ BERD@NFDI (NFDI Consortium for Business, Economic and Related Data), <https://www.berd-nfdi.de/>.

information protection then happened, according to Lamdan, partly through the silent boycott of companies, which buried the information they were obliged to report in PR debris, and partly through datafication, which rewards whoever can play the speed advantage. Protected access to information becomes almost useless under digital conditions, because the high-priced service delivers the best summary already at the push of a button, thus justifying dependencies and half-secret practices, e.g., to circumvent regulations against insider trading (see p. 109).

Lamdan does not discuss in detail that financial data products also have a close relationship with risk assessment, i.e., data brokering for the target group of decision-makers. This is clear from databases such as Thomson Reuters World-Check (now Refinitiv), which list so-called PEPs, 'Politically Exposed Persons'. The official purpose of these products is, among other things, to minimize money laundering: If a person appears at a Credit Suisse branch asking for a discreet account and holding out the prospect of a lot of money, bank employees are supposed to use such tools to check whether they are dealing with the son-in-law of a kleptocrat or an oligarch's daughter. Now, among other things, the research on the *Panama Papers*¹² and the *Swiss Secrets*¹³ have shown that the account is very likely to be opened, no matter what is in these databases. However, the investigative journalists also revealed a lot of tracking data when looking into products provided by such data brokers: which mobile devices are connected to which person, for example? Which device is the Whatsapp account linked to? Which radio cell does the device log into?¹⁴ As little as data cartels care about the 99% in their social bias, they seem to be evolving into a service infrastructure for the 1%.

Both Thomson Reuters and RELX (formerly Reed Elsevier) also have strong roots in the news business. In her concluding chapter, Lamdan addresses the situation in this field, which she sees as characterized by a dualism: if news is an essential public resource for an enlightened democratic society on the one hand, it also serves as fodder for data analytics tools on the other. Whereas news, like legal information, was long protected, in this case by a public domain, today news, like legal and research information, can be linked to other data for predictive products (see p. 112).

In her historical derivation, Lamdan sees public news as an important part of the information infrastructures of vital democracies with corresponding trust capital; digitization in the news sector, by contrast, has had disastrous consequences: In less than a decade, she says, the U.S. newspaper industry lost more than half of its employees, mainly affecting the 'provinces' that lost all access to local news. Before that, since the 1970s, under the influence of the Chicago School, public news had already lost considerable ground (cf. p. 114). With the spread of the Internet, the protection of public news stations was deliberately weakened once again, until even Sesame Street disappeared behind the paywall.

The news sector thus behaved no differently under the rule of the data cartels than other information sectors: "private companies swoop in and take over information infrastructure that

¹² Cf. Obermayer, Bastian; Obermaier, Frederik: *Panama Papers. Die Geschichte einer weltweiten Enthüllung*, Köln 2021.

¹³ Cf. Munzinger, Hannes; Obermaier, Frederik; Obermayer, Bastian: *Schweizer Geheimnisse. Wie Banker das Geld von Steuerhinterziehern, Foltergenerälen, Diktatoren und der katholischen Kirche versteckt haben – mit Hilfe der Politik*, Köln 2022.

¹⁴ See Munzinger et.al. 2022, p. 162ff.

the public fails to adequately support." (p. 117) Tracking in the news sector is even more developed than in the science sector;¹⁵ user data and clicks count, not product quality, and democratic discourse is fading, as recent years have shown.

In her concluding remarks, Sarah Lamdan brings together some points that she considers central to finding a way out of the current situation:

- Don't think in terms of your own particular line of business, but look at data cartels as a whole. Their fundamental structure, the force they draw from their economies of scale, would not become clear if they were viewed as publishers, for example, simply because they once were, among other things.
- Information would have to be regarded as a public good, and information infrastructures would thus have to be promoted and organized in the same way as public roads and water pipes.
- Companies would have to be better controlled and oligopolies avoided. The current situation is reminiscent of the 'Gilded Age,' the predatory capitalism of the late 19th century. The previous exceptionalism in the digital sector, that something cannot be regulated simply because it is technology, must be ended.
- Competition must be encouraged and protected to prevent the monopolization of entire markets. Monopolization also promotes disadvantages due to errors: The mass of information flowing in overwhelms the tech companies and causes quality losses in their products.
- Access to information must be possible without data exploration. Otherwise, Open Access would remain an ambiguous key: there must be a separation between the information infrastructures and the data analytics structures. Then Open Access could also work with private owners.

One of the problems that emerges here is, of course, this: building a road can be put out to tender as a public contract, just like a ferry line. But what about an infrastructure as complex as GitHub? Any substitutability of providers will reach its limits there. Add to that the fact that data itself is not infrastructure, according to Lamdan's account, but the Internet is. Data companies are therefore not utilities (but could still be regulated accordingly, like radio stations, for example), and data is also always unique, unlike electricity and tap water. For information, her proposal is therefore a digital library, supported by central public funds derived from taxation of big tech: Tax loopholes should be closed in favor of a public digital infrastructure - the Internet Archive or the Hathi Trust are examples that the public sector should emulate.

Data Cartels bundles together a lot of information painstakingly gathered through freedom of information requests, scattered in tweets, blogs, corporate writings and a host of other reports that would once have been lumped under the heading of gray literature. Sarah Lamdan is to be

¹⁵ For example, Richard Gutjahr researched 470 trackers on the website sueddeutsche.de, cf. Richard Gutjahr: Der Cookie Wahnsinn. Cookie-Fallen – wir pfeifen auf Ihre Privatsphäre, 11.12.2020, <https://www.gutjahr.biz/2020/12/wir-pfeifen-auf-ihre-privatsphaere/>.

thanked for piecing together this widely scattered puzzle, giving us a coherent account, uncomfortable as it is for us. We look at it with a similar shiver as we would an episode of *Black Mirror*. Yet it has long been the *Truman Show* of us all.